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Prof. D.T. Lakdawala Memorial Lecture¹

on

POVERTY, INEQUALITY AND GROWTH: REVIEWING THE PAST AND LOOKING AHEAD

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It is an honour to be invited to deliver the D.T. Lakdawala Memorial Lecture. Prof. Lakdawala founded the Sardar Patel Institute of Economic and Social Research and he was one of the most distinguished economists of his generation. He had deep interest in the measurement of poverty and made important contributions to the national debate in this area. Since it is in this context that I first met him, allow me to begin by recalling that occasion.

It was in 1978 when I was working in the World Bank in Washington DC and visiting Delhi on holidays. I called on Yoginder K. Alagh, another stalwart from the Sardar Patel Institute, who was then the Advisor for the Perspective Planning Division, Planning Commission of India. In the course of the meeting, I mentioned that I was doing some empirical work on trends in rural poverty in India arising out of Pranab Bardhan's 1971 paper which showed that rural poverty had increased between 1960-61 and 1967-68 (Ahluwalia, 1978). Bardhan's result was contrary to the findings of B.S. Minhas who found a steady decline and the Bardhan paper was often quoted as demonstrating the failure of our growth strategy. I had a different view. I felt rural poverty was affected by the level of agricultural production per head of the rural population in the same year and also with one year lag and on this basis I felt the high poverty in 1967-68 did not reflect a trend increase but could be explained by the fact that agricultural production per head of the rural population was very low in 1967-68 and also in the previous year.

Since rural poverty was of particular importance at the time, Yoginder invited me to make a presentation in the Commission. I readily accepted, viewing it as a privilege. Imagine my surprise when I arrived for the presentation and found that Prof. Lakdawala himself—who was then the Deputy Chairman of the Planning Commission—on hearing of the subject, decided to preside over

¹Dr. Montek Singh Ahluwalia delivered Prof. D.T. Lakdawala Memorial Lecture which was held on February 22, 2025 at the Sardar Patel Institute of Economic and Social Research, Ahmedabad.

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